

0.4 KV CABLE NETWORKS AND THEIR REQUIREMENTS

Ergashev Abdurasul Abdumutallib o'g'li

Andijan machine building Institute, Uzbekistan, 170119,

Andijan city. 56 Baburshokh Street

e-mail: **abdurasulergashev0102@gmail.com**

ANNOTATION

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The main component in the construction of power transmission lines is cable and conductor products. AVVG cable is characterized by low weight, simplicity and reliability of the design. These useful qualities, along with low prices, determine the popularity of the product and its active use in various areas of life - from household to industry. Conductors successfully cope with the transmission of electricity in AC and DC networks.

Due to technical parameters, AVVG can work in any climatic zones of our country, and weather conditions do not affect durability and safety.

Figure 1: AVVG cable view

AVVG is an abbreviation with a unique decoding feature according to GOST. Assign a value to each letter:

- "A" - aluminum (material for the production of a conductive core);
- "B" (first) - PVC film (for core insulation);
- "B" (second) - PVC plastic for the outer shell;
- "G" - bare (the cable does not have additional protection).

Prefixes in the form of other letters are often added to AVVG with a hyphen - for example, "T" or "P". The first indicates that the wire is designed for use in the tropics (it fights mold well), the second indicates that the product is flat.

Numeric values are written after the letter symbol.

For example, AVVG-220 4 * 30 is an aluminum cable with polyvinyl chloride core insulation and outer covering, designed for operation in a 220 V network, consisting of four cores with a section of 30 square meters. mm. The prefix "OJ" can be added in parentheses, which indicates that the cores are made of single wire.

Technical characteristics of AVVG 4*240 cable:

Weight: 1km = 5561 kg.

Electrical characteristics:

Nominal alternating voltage: 0.66/1 kV

Nominal frequency: 50 Hz

Inductive resistance: 0.0587 Ohm/km

Active resistance: 0.132 Ohm/km

In normal and overload operation at 100% load factor:

In air: 369 Amps

On Ground: 355 Amps

Marking of power cables with PVC insulation

Now learn more about the designation of various modifications of the AVVG power cable, based on which you can make a brief description of each product.

LETTERMARKING:

The first letter in the name of the electrical product does not change, so the cores of such a cable are made only of aluminum. If this letter is not present (on other wire brands), then the cores are made of copper.

In addition to AVVG, there are other modifications - AVVP, APVG, AVBbShv , APvBbShv , etc. Depending on the position, one or another letter indicates a certain design feature:

The letter in the second place describes the material of production of

insulation of individual cores. As mentioned above, "V" is polyvinyl chloride, "P" is polyethylene, "Pv" (if the letter is small, it means the capital letter standing to its left) is vulcanized polyethylene. Another feature is that in the absence of "A", the second character is first (VVG), which means that each letter of this list moves one position to the left.

The symbol in the third position describes the material from which the sheath of the entire wire is made. "B" - polyvinyl chloride, "A" - aluminum, "Bb" - armored protection made of steel or galvanized tape.

The letter in the fourth position describes the presence of additional protection in the cable. The symbol "G" indicates its absence, in which case the wire is called bare. The letters " SH " indicate that the additional outer covering is PVC hose.

In addition to ozh ", the abbreviation can have the following meanings:

ng - the product does not support ignition;

LS - during combustion, production materials emit a minimal amount of smoke and harmful gases;

LTx - toxic or slightly toxic substances do not evaporate during combustion.

NUMERICAL MARKING: From the example discussed above, it is clear that the first number after the letter symbol indicates the nominal voltage in volts. Sometimes it is displayed in kilovolts. Then the abbreviation looks like this - AVVG-0.22. Then follow the numbers that describe the number of current-carrying cores and show their cross-section (they all have the same cross-section).

CABLE STRUCTURE: The electrical product has a simple structure. Conductors are made of high quality aluminum. Their number varies from one to six. They are single-wire (monolithic) or multi-wire. In the first case, the letter "ozh" is added to the symbol. If these signs are not present, then the cable is multi-wired.

Insulation is color coded according to generally accepted international standards. The blue shell indicates the "zero" conductor, yellow-green or brown - grounding, red - phase. If the cable has several phases, then other colors are selected - black, orange, green, purple, etc.

When constructing a cross-sectional diagram of an AVVG cable, a different color code is used: red indicates the cable insulation, yellow indicates the core, and black indicates the outer shell.

Many product manufacturers add duct tape between the outer sheath and the rest of the cable. With its help, quick, fast and safe removal of the shell is ensured. In a two-core cable, the sections of the current-carrying cores are always the same, in other cases the value may differ. Often, the earth or neutral core has a smaller cross-section, but in a six-core AVVG cable, the cross-section for both is smaller.

TECHNICAL CHARACTERISTICS:

Now in more detail about the technical characteristics and operating conditions of the AVVG cable:

working voltage - 600/1000 V;

current frequency in alternating networks - 50 Hz;

core section - 2.5-250 square meters. mm;

operating temperature range - from -50 to +50 gr. Celsius;

the maximum permissible main heating temperature is +70 gr. Celsius;

temperature range during assembly work - from -15 to +50 gr. Celsius;

term of service - 30 years;

warranty period - 5 years;

bending radius - depends on the outer diameter.

The following table shows all models of AVVG cable with the maximum value of continuous current, insulation thickness, product weight and resistance value:

CHARACTERISTICS OF TECHNICAL USE: AVVG is used in many areas of life. It is an indispensable electrical component in the construction of distribution substations in industrial facilities, in the installation of local power transmission lines. It is often used for laying wires in residential buildings and production workshops.

During the laying and use of the AVVG cable, it is necessary to ensure the absence of mechanical and compression damage, since the product is not protected by an armored tape. The wire is very sensitive to stretching, which can damage the PVC insulation layer. Thus, minimum sag should be ensured during laying on walls or supporting columns.

If you need to lay it on the ground, then you should buy a cable marked with AVVGz. These products differ from the usual AVVG wire in a denser arrangement of cores. To reduce the space, a PVC compound is added inside, which is also used to produce the outer shell. To begin with, a trench is dug, then a sand cushion is created, and after that the cable is laid. After making sure that there are no tensions, the road is covered with a layer of sand with a thickness of at least 150 mm.

Important! Regardless of the type of cable chosen, additional protection with signal tape is required when laying on the ground. Its thickness and length are chosen so that it completely covers the cable in width and length. In places where a large load may fall on the ground, the conductor is protected by a metal pipe.

AVVGng cable is an ideal option for organizing electrical networks in facilities with high fire safety requirements, where non-combustible products are needed. The "ng" prefix means no burning, even if the components are laid out in bundles.

WHERE IT CAN BE USED: AVVG-cable with a small cross-section of cores is actively used in the household sector - up to 6 square meters. mm. The

presence of two protective layers (core insulation and outer coating) allows the product to be used for open cable channels. On the other hand, the plastic box retains the aesthetics, so it is still recommended to use it. If you plan to organize hidden wires, then the wire must be hidden inside the corrugation.

The PVC compound allows resistance to ultraviolet rays, so the AVVG cable can be placed even on the street, in the open air. The design of the wire allows you to protect it from dust and moisture, so you can safely equip electrical circuits in more humid places - basements, basements and places with a high probability of mold.

Tip! AVVG cannot be used in steam rooms, bathrooms and other similar places, because the upper limit of the working temperature is +50 gr. Celsius. It is known that the average air temperature in the steam room is approximately +90 degrees. Celsius.

STORAGE AND TRANSPORT REQUIREMENTS:

The cable is supplied and stored in special wooden drums. During the winding process, the ends of the wire are fixed on the "cheek" of the drum, which makes it easier to check the product. The storage period of AVVG depends on the following conditions:

- outdoors - 2 years;
- under canopies in pavilions - 5 years;
- in specialized warehouses - 10 years.

Do not confuse drums with bays. However, AVVG can be transported and stored in the second one, but one must weigh up to 25 kg. In addition, the coil is filled with packaging that excludes arbitrary opening. Regardless of the choice, a label or technical passport is attached to the product hidden in a waterproof shell.

cable selection AVVG: The main criterion for cable selection is the operating conditions. The first thing you should pay attention to is the number of cores. Here are some basic selection tips:

it is recommended to use AVVG with two or three cores in single-phase networks (the presence or absence of a PE conductor affects the final choice);
in three phases - three or four (presence / absence of grounding);
when replacing electrical equipment with local control - from five to six cores.

Tip! Make sure that quality certificates are available to increase safety and ensure that you receive a quality product with the declared technical and operational characteristics.

The cross-section of the current-carrying conductors of the cable depends on the expected current load. Follow the information in the table below to make a decision:

As for the length of the wire, it depends on the distance between the connected objects, the presence of bends and turns in the route. Do not forget about the absence of voltage when laying on the ground.

CHECKING AVVG QUALITY IN LABORATORY CONDITIONS

Various quality control methods are used to confirm compliance with specified technical and operational requirements. It is better to give the cable for testing in specialized laboratories.

First, its external condition is checked: make sure there are no cracks or other signs of mechanical damage. Next, the number of cores in the section is counted, the color of their insulation is recorded, after which the obtained data is compared with the data in the technical documents attached to the product. Then more laborious checks begin: the number of wires of each core is taken into account (if it is not a monolithic cable with the prefix " ozh ").

In the laboratory, they make sure that there are no breaks in the insulation, they check its strength. An ohmmeter and a multimeter allow you to determine resistance.

AVVG cable installation methods

There are two main ways of installing electrical wiring - hidden and open. In addition, one of the types of hidden electrical wiring is laying the cable on the ground. Consider the characteristics of each option using the AVVG cable.

List of used literature

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